

From Nature-Inspired Innovation to Nature Conservation and Restoration Financing

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“My family’s fishing legacy is the epitome of talent, to the point that we are revered as “king.” Only today did I learn that, apparently, the whole family has been catching fish illegally.”

—In “Family Legacy...”; *Wild Wise Weird* (2024)

Abstract

Biomimicry—the practice of emulating nature’s time-tested patterns and strategies—has yielded transformative innovations across sectors, from energy-efficient transport to advanced materials and medical devices. Yet this rapid growth in nature-inspired innovation unfolds against the backdrop of an accelerating biodiversity crisis. This paradox highlights an “innovation debt” to nature: humanity benefits from ecosystems’ intellectual capital while their degradation undermines the very knowledge base upon which future solutions depend. This perspective advances a profit-sharing mechanism to reinvest a portion of biomimicry-derived revenues into biodiversity conservation and restoration. Grounded in the semiconducting principle—which permits conversion of environmental value into monetary gain but prohibits monetary gain from offsetting environmental loss—the model operationalizes benefit-sharing through a five-step process: identification, contribution calculation, payment and pooling, allocation, and accountability. Contributions, proportionate to commercial success, would be directed to priority projects, with allocations reflecting both the origin of inspiration and conservation urgency. The proposed framework can help address the biodiversity finance gap, embed nature as a stakeholder in enterprise, and foster an eco-surplus culture in which business success and ecological regeneration advance together. In doing so, it creates a feedback loop where the more we innovate like nature, the more we invest in sustaining it.

Keywords: biomimicry; nature-inspired innovation; biodiversity conservation; knowledge; semiconducting principle; eco-surplus culture.

1. Biomimicry's Promise and the Biodiversity Imperative

Biomimicry, a term popularized by Janine Benyus in 1997, refers to the practice of learning and emulating patterns, strategies, and systems developed, evolved, and refined by living organisms over 3.8 billion years to address human challenges (Benyus, 1997). Rather than focusing on resource extraction, biomimicry poses a different question: What can we learn from nature? The breadth of its promise is reflected in countless innovations. For example, Japan's Shinkansen bullet train overcame the problem of noisy tunnel sonic booms by adopting the streamlined beak shape of the kingfisher, allowing it to travel 10% faster while consuming 15% less electricity (Baker, 2025). Velcro, another iconic case, emerged when a Swiss engineer replicated the tiny hook structures of burrs that clung to his dog's fur in 1941, later founding the Velcro company in 1959. Since then, Velcro has become integrated into human daily lives and transformed the fastener industry (Micro Photonics, 2020). Other examples include energy-efficient buildings modeled on termite mounds' natural cooling systems and medical adhesives inspired by the microstructures of gecko feet (Klein, 2019; Liu et al., 2024). Across transportation, architecture, materials science, medicine, and beyond, biomimicry has generated sustainable, high-performance solutions, demonstrating how harnessing nature's time-tested strategies can transform human technology and industry (Hayes et al., 2020; Kennedy et al., 2015; Lurie-Luke, 2014).

Given its tremendous potential, biomimicry's applications are expanding rapidly. Over recent decades, the field has grown exponentially, evolving from a niche research interest into a mainstream innovation strategy (Lebdioui, 2022). The global market for biomimetic materials alone—excluding numerous innovations in other fields—was valued at USD 37.9 billion in 2020 and is projected to reach USD 65.9 billion by 2030 (Dixit & Prasad, 2021). Major corporations, including Boeing, Nike, and Procter & Gamble, have collaborated with biomimicry experts to redesign products and processes for greater efficiency and sustainability. Dedicated innovation programs and accelerators, such as the Biomimicry Institute's Ray of Hope Accelerator, now scout nature-inspired start-ups, attracting 250–300 applications annually (Baker, 2025).

Yet this growth is shadowed by a profound paradox. While biomimicry is increasingly recognized as a viable development pathway—and nature as an unparalleled knowledge bank for addressing both present and unforeseen challenges—the biodiversity crisis is accelerating at an unprecedented rate (Lebdioui, 2022; Vuong, La, et al., 2025). Human activities, including habitat destruction, pollution, and anthropogenic climate change, are exerting immense pressures on Earth’s ecosystems, driving alarming declines in species and habitats (WWF, 2024). The landmark 2019 IPBES assessment warned that up to one million plant and animal species face extinction, many within decades, due to anthropogenic impacts (IPBES, 2019). This rapid biodiversity loss is not only an ecological tragedy; it undermines the very foundation of human society, including its knowledge base. Each lost species or degraded ecosystem could represent an undiscovered innovation—whether for medicine, engineering, or climate adaptation—that humanity will never recover.

The central argument of this perspective is that the financial gains from biomimicry innovations should be reinvested into protecting and restoring biodiversity. Humanity benefits enormously from nature-inspired designs; ethically and pragmatically, a portion of those profits should be allocated to sustaining the natural systems that made these innovations possible. Such reinvestment would create a regenerative cycle in which ideas drawn from nature generate value, and that value is returned to nature through targeted conservation and restoration funding. This model also addresses what can be termed humanity’s innovation debt to the natural world. The rationale of this model rests on the semiconducting principle of environmental and monetary value exchange, which permits the conversion of environmental value into monetary gains but prohibits using monetary gains to justify environmental degradation (Vuong, 2021). Within this framework, profits derived from biomimicry carry an inherent environmental obligation—one that can be repaid by allocating a portion of these gains to the conservation and restoration of biodiversity.

In the sections that follow, we elaborate on the semiconducting principle, assess the current state of benefit-sharing in biomimicry, and outline a mechanism for channeling biomimicry-derived profits toward an eco-surplus future—one in which business prosperity and ecological integrity advance together.

2. The Semiconducting Principle: Bridging Environmental Value and Monetary Value

Modern economic systems generally fail to account for nature's value, treating environmental benefits as externalities (Keen, 2023; La et al., 2025; Vuong, Nguyen, et al., 2025). The semiconducting principle offers a conceptual reframe by formally coupling environmental and monetary value in economic accounting. At its core, this principle redefines profit in dual terms:

$$\text{New Net Profit (NNP)} = \text{Net Monetary Profit (NMP)} + \text{Net Environmental Value (NEV)}$$

Under this framework, a business's "bottom line" would include not only financial returns to shareholders but also measurable ecological gains. Net Environmental Value (NEV) captures positive ecological impacts, such as hectares of habitat restored, tons of carbon sequestered, volumes of water purified, etc.—whether achieved intentionally or as a byproduct of operations. Net Monetary Profit (NMP) is the conventional measure of financial profit (Vuong, 2021).

The semiconducting principle establishes one-way convertibility: environmental value may be recognized or converted into monetary gain, but monetary gain cannot be deemed equivalent to environmental value. This asymmetry, analogous to a diode allowing current to flow in only one direction, ensures that financial success does not justify ecological harm. For instance, a company producing a nature-inspired water filtration system might be credited for quantifiable ecosystem benefits such as improved water quality and biodiversity. However, high financial profits alone would not offset environmental damage elsewhere in its operations. Existing mechanisms such as carbon trading lack this one-way safeguard; they often allow emissions to be "offset" by financial payments, effectively treating money as commensurate with ecological restoration (Vuong, Nguyen, et al., 2025). In a true semiconducting system, only genuine, verifiable environmental gains would count toward the profit equation, preventing firms from relying on monetary outlays to claim "green" credentials without delivering actual ecological benefit.

Adopting the semiconducting principle can foster the socio-economic transitions toward an eco-surplus culture, where companies actively create surplus environmental value alongside financial returns, and society rewards them for doing so (Vuong & Nguyen, 2024). Adopting the principle institutionalizes the norm that value created for the environment is rewarded with money, but not vice versa. For example, a biomimetic agricultural technique that restores soil health and biodiversity could receive credits, subsidies, tax incentives, or market advantages proportionate to the ecological gains achieved. Crucially, these benefits accrue only from nature-positive outcomes; monetary success cannot compensate for nature-negative impacts.

Biomimicry-linked revenue allocation provides a practical pathway to operationalize this principle. Because biomimicry draws directly on the “intellectual capital” of nature, such innovations inherently carry a debt to nature. Channeling a defined share of biomimicry-derived profits into conservation and restoration initiatives would recognize and reward nature’s contributions—be they inspiration, genetic information, or ecosystem-based insights. In effect, the environment’s role as a co-innovator receives tangible monetary recompense. Currently, this transfer rarely occurs. Nature’s patterns, forms, and processes are effectively open-access intellectual property: they can be appropriated freely without compensation to the ecosystems or species from which they originate (Nguyen, 2024). Consequently, environmental benefits from biomimetic processes—such as waste reduction or improved water quality—are seldom monetized or systematically rewarded.

Establishing a policy or norm that companies profiting from bio-inspired innovation must invest a proportion of those profits into environmental causes would convert implicit environmental value into concrete financial support for nature conservation and restoration. This approach makes the NNP formula actionable: the NEV component would be represented by funds directed toward verified conservation or restoration projects, proportional to the innovation’s commercial success. Such a framework ensures environmental value can be converted into monetary recognition while preventing monetary wealth from excusing environmental degradation.

In the next section, we examine whether current biomimicry practices incorporate such benefit-sharing and where gaps remain—underscoring the need for intentional mechanisms to embed the semiconducting principle in practice.

3. Biomimicry’s Economic Benefits: Current Profit Distribution and the Conservation Gap

Biomimetic innovations already generate substantial economic value, yet there is currently no systematic mechanism for channeling these profits into biodiversity conservation or ecosystem restoration. The prevailing situation is one of uncaptured value: companies and inventors secure monetary rewards from nature-inspired products, while the source ecosystems and species receive little to no direct benefit. Unlike cases involving bioprospecting or access to genetic resources—which may trigger benefit-sharing obligations under international agreements such as the Nagoya Protocol—pure biomimicry often relies on intangible inspiration: the observation and imitation of natural phenomena. This process typically falls outside existing legal frameworks for compensation. As a result, the environmental knowledge and value underpinning such innovations remain uncompensated in financial terms—there is, in effect, no “royalty” paid to nature (Lebdioui, 2022).

At present, most profits from biomimicry accrue to private firms, inventors, and investors. A nature-inspired product or architectural design can be patented, licensed, and sold like any other intellectual property, generating revenue streams entirely within conventional market channels—yet nature, which provided the conceptual blueprint, is not acknowledged as a stakeholder. While some mechanisms indirectly link biomimicry-related profits to conservation efforts, these are limited in scope and largely voluntary.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Philanthropy. Some corporations engaged in biomimicry by making direct charitable donations to environmental causes or developing sustainability programs. For example, Interface—the carpet manufacturer renowned for its biomimetic designs—has invested heavily in sustainability and

launched initiatives such as Net-Works, which purchases discarded fishing nets for recycling, benefiting both coastal communities and marine ecosystems (Interface, 2019; Khoo et al., 2021). However, such actions are discretionary rather than formalized profit-sharing with nature, typically driven by corporate values or public relations strategies rather than an obligation tied to the biomimetic patent itself.

Green Marketing and ESG Pressures. Firms may allocate a portion of profits to conservation projects to strengthen brand identity or meet Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) expectations. For instance, a company might sponsor a wildlife reserve or fund a tree-planting campaign, especially if its brand emphasizes being “inspired by nature.” While beneficial, these contributions are voluntary and inconsistent, with no standardized requirement or percentage of biomimicry-derived revenue dedicated to such efforts.

Benefit-Sharing in Biotech and Pharmaceuticals (Limited Scope). In biotechnology and pharmaceuticals, when products are derived from genetic resources (e.g., a drug developed from a rainforest plant), the Convention on Biological Diversity and its Nagoya Protocol require “fair and equitable” benefit-sharing with the provider country or community. A well-known example is the 1991 agreement in which Merck, a major United States pharmaceutical company, paid Costa Rica’s INBio for access to its biodiversity for drug discovery, with a promise to provide royalties if any commercial products were developed (Coughlin Jr, 1993). However, these frameworks primarily apply to bioprospecting—where physical samples are extracted—and traditional knowledge (Buck & Hamilton, 2011). Biomimicry often involves no physical genetic material, relying instead on observations or images. Consequently, Nagoya Protocol provisions are difficult to enforce: companies are not obliged to disclose the origin of their inspiration, and tracing the source is rarely possible (Feng, 2017). This gap enables what some Robinson (2010) describes as biopiracy— “[t]he patenting of (often spurious) inventions based on biological resources and/or traditional knowledge that are extracted without adequate authorization and benefit sharing from other (usually developing countries), indigenous or local communities.”

Lack of Intellectual Property Recognition for Nature. Intellectual property law does not recognize nature—or the communities that steward it—as an inventor in biomimicry. Patents are granted to human applicants, even when the invention is a direct imitation of a biological model. Although patents require novelty, translating a natural mechanism into a human-made product can still be deemed novel and non-obvious under patent law. There is no obligation for patentees to identify the natural source or share royalties with the source country or a conservation fund. In effect, biodiversity’s informational inputs remain in the public domain, freely available for appropriation without financial recognition (Lebdioui, 2022; Tria et al., 2014).

Given these gaps, it is unsurprising that few formal mechanisms exist to channel biomimicry profits back into biodiversity conservation. This represents a missed opportunity to repay nature for the environmental value it provides. Innovators benefit from nature’s R&D, yet nature receives none of the profits. Meanwhile, biodiversity loss continues—underfunded by the same society that profits from its inspiration.

In summary, a persistent gap remains between the profits generated by biomimicry and the financing of biodiversity conservation. Current systems fail to translate environmental value into monetary flows back to nature. The prevailing mindset still frames nature protection as a cost or charitable act, rather than as an inherent share of the profits that nature helped create. The semiconducting principle challenges this view: environmental value should be explicitly recognized in monetary terms and rewarded accordingly, requiring dedicated channels for directing a portion of the revenue earned because of nature back to nature itself. The next section outlines how this can be institutionalized—by earmarking a share of biomimicry patent revenues or profits for conservation and restoration—thereby laying the groundwork for an eco-surplus culture.

4. Financing Conservation via Biomimicry Profits: A Framework for Eco-Surplus

Envisioning a mechanism to allocate biomimicry-derived profits toward biodiversity conservation and restoration, we draw on emerging ideas in policy and practice. A notable precedent comes from ongoing negotiations under the CBD. At the CBD's COP16 in Cali, Colombia (2024), delegates advanced the proposal for a Cali Biodiversity Fund designed to capture a share of profits from the use of Digital Sequence Information on Genetic Resources. Initially, the fund expects that large entities deriving substantial commercial benefits from the use of digital sequence information will contribute 1% of profits or 0.1% of revenues to biodiversity conservation. These funds would be directed to developing countries, as well as to Indigenous peoples and local communities, to support the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity (CBD et al., 2025). This represents a tangible step toward monetizing environmental value while advancing equity. Importantly, the Biomimicry Institute, in collaboration with New York University's More-Than-Human Life legal program, has proposed extending this model to include bio-inspired innovations beyond DNA-based products—such as sharkskin-inspired coatings or beetle-inspired pigments—so that a similar share of revenues supports conservation (Baker, 2025).

Building on this idea, we propose a biomimicry benefit-sharing mechanism with the following participants and roles:

Global Biodiversity Innovation Fund. Establish an international fund (or integrate with the CBD's Cali Fund) dedicated to conservation and ecological restoration, financed through a levy on biomimicry-based products. The fund could be administered by an existing body (e.g., Global Environment Facility) or a new public–private partnership. The contribution rate from net profits should be carefully calibrated—high enough to generate substantial resources for biodiversity conservation projects, yet modest enough to remain politically and economically feasible. Functioning like royalty on Mother Nature's intellectual property, this mechanism would see companies effectively paying a dividend back to the ecosystems that inspired their products.

Governments. National governments could mandate or incentivize these contributions by integrating requirements into patent law (for certain classes of biologically inspired patents) or corporate sustainability reporting frameworks. Incentives such as tax credits or expedited patent examination could encourage early voluntary adoption. Eventually, countries could align regulations with CBD decisions, requiring benefit-sharing from firms using biological resources or knowledge. Governments could also identify priority conservation projects aligned with national biodiversity strategies, and biodiversity-rich countries could advocate strongly for a fair share of benefits.

International Organizations. The CBD, World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), and multilateral development banks could provide governance, technical support, and oversight. The CBD's Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework already highlights the need to close a \$700 billion annual biodiversity financing gap (CBD, 2022). An international protocol could formalize biomimicry profit-sharing as one innovative financing stream. WIPO could create a dedicated category for biomimetic patents, tagging them for benefit-sharing obligations. A multi-stakeholder board—including scientists, Indigenous representatives, conservation NGOs, and industry—could ensure transparent allocation and effective project selection.

Businesses and Inventors. Companies would shift from viewing conservation funding as charity or liability to treating it as a licensing fee or reinvestment in the natural R&D systems they draw from. Framing contributions as innovation insurance would highlight that biodiversity underpins future solutions. Some firms might go beyond the minimum requirement, branding themselves as “biodiversity-positive” by allocating, for example, 5% of biomimetic profits to conservation. Businesses could also link contributions to the ecosystems that inspired their products (e.g., coral-inspired designs funding coral reef restoration), strengthening values, impacts, and brand storytelling.

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Indigenous Communities. NGOs and Indigenous/local community organizations would be primary recipients and stewards of funds, setting priorities such as land acquisition for reserves, ranger programs, habitat restoration, and sustainable livelihood initiatives. They could also support independent auditing to ensure transparency and accountability. Given that Indigenous

knowledge has often indirectly inspired biomimicry, equitable benefit-sharing for them is also essential. Consistent with the COP16 proposal, at least half of the Cali Biodiversity Fund should go to Indigenous peoples and local communities in biodiversity-rich regions—ensuring fairness and empowering these communities to continue their role as guardians of nature (CBD et al., 2025).

In practical terms, implementing a biomimicry profit-sharing scheme could follow a five-step process: (1) Identification, (2) Contribution Calculation, (3) Payment and Pooling, (4) Fund Allocation, and (5) Accountability.

1. **Identification:** Companies or patent applicants would declare whether a product or patent is biologically inspired. This disclosure could be incentivized through positive recognition—such as a “BioInspired” certification—or, over time, mandated by law in specific sectors, similar to requirements in some jurisdictions for disclosing the origin of genetic resources.
2. **Contribution Calculation:** A standardized formula would be applied (e.g., annually, 1% of net profit attributable to the product). The figure could be reported in annual reports or submitted to a central registry.
3. **Payment and Pooling:** Contributions would be paid into an international biodiversity fund, or into national funds where such exist. National funds could then channel resources toward global conservation programs or targeted local projects.
4. **Fund Allocation:** An independent council would be needed to direct funds to priority initiatives such as protecting critical habitats, restoring degraded ecosystems, supporting species recovery programs, or conducting environmental research. Allocation could consider both the origin of the biological inspiration (ensuring benefits return to that region, where traceable) and the urgency of conservation needs (e.g., threatened biodiversity hotspots).
5. **Accountability:** Annual public reports would detail total contributions and measurable conservation outcomes (e.g., dollars per acre of habitat preserved,

number of trees planted). This transparent feedback loop reinforces the mechanism's value and enables companies to integrate these outcomes into their sustainability narratives, demonstrating tangible benefits to consumers.

If this mechanism is successfully implemented, it will also foster the eco-surplus culture in business, as envisioned in the semiconducting principle. By structurally linking innovation profits to environmental regeneration, it fosters a cultural shift from “do no harm” to “deliver net good.”

Consider a scenario a decade from now: a startup develops a solar panel coating patterned after butterfly wings, dramatically improving light capture efficiency. The product becomes a commercial success. Under an eco-surplus norm, the company proudly allocates a share of its earnings to butterfly habitat conservation and pollinator-friendly agriculture. Its marketing emphasizes that the more successful the product, the more butterflies and ecosystems flourish—transforming profit-seeking into regeneration-seeking. Consumers, in turn, prefer products that actively give back to nature. Investors begin valuing companies not only by quarterly profit but also by Net Environmental Value contributions. Boardroom discussions expand from “What is our quarterly profit?” to “What is our net environmental value this quarter, and how can we increase it?” This represents a fundamental cultural shift toward recognizing nature as a foundation for social progress and a legitimate stakeholder in enterprise.

Achieving this vision will require sustained, coordinated effort among a society with a high Nature Quotient (Vuong & Nguyen, 2025). Key challenges include establishing equitable contribution levels, preventing greenwashing by ensuring that payments translate into verifiable conservation outcomes, and securing international alignment so that no major economy becomes a haven for companies avoiding such obligations. These challenges, however, are surmountable with strong political will and broad public support. For companies, the expense—representing only a small fraction of profits—is negligible when set against the immense costs humanity will face if biodiversity loss continues unchecked. Moreover, such costs can often be offset through modest price adjustments, as the public increasingly recognizes and values the positive environmental contributions embedded in these products. In a world where the global

community is striving to mobilize hundreds of billions of dollars for conservation, channeling a portion of this financing from the returns generated by nature's own ingenuity—through biomimicry innovations—offers a far more sustainable and resilient pathway than relying solely on philanthropy or the limited capacity of government budgets.

Transitioning from nature-inspired innovation to nature conservation financing is not merely aspirational rhetoric; it is a practical imperative in the Anthropocene. Biomimicry has delivered cleaner technologies, more efficient systems, and breakthrough solutions precisely because it emulates nature's time-tested strategies. It is essential to reciprocate that debt. Embedding the semiconducting principle into economic systems—rewarding environmental gains while prohibiting monetary compensation from legitimizing irreversible ecological loss—would help cultivate an eco-surplus era, where business success and biodiversity recovery advance together. The proposed profit-sharing mechanism for biomimicry patents offers a concrete pathway toward this goal, creating a self-reinforcing loop in which innovation sustains the very ecological processes that inspire it.

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